
A model of noisy attitude for cycle 3 simulations

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1 Overview

This document describes the proposal of the implementation of an “attitude with filtered white noise” to be used in cycle 3 simulations, covering the simulation request SR-CU3-3-F-GAIASIMU-001 ([XL07]).

2 Reference documents

References

- [BB05] U. Bastian and M. Biermann. Astrometric meaning and interpretation of high-precision time delay integration CCD data. *A&A*, 438:745–755, August 2005.
- [XL07] C. Babusiaux X. Luri. Consolidated list of simulation requirements and planning for cycle 3. Technical report, UB/ObsPM, 2007. GAIA-C2-SP-UB-XL-004.
- [YI06] X. Luri Y. Isasi, E. Masana. Gaia system simulator overview. Technical report, UB, 2006. GAIA-C2-TN-UB-YI-001-1.

3 Physical model of the Gaia attitude

3.1 Spacecraft dynamics

A complete dynamical model of the attitude of the Gaia spacecraft is being developed by S. Theil and collaborators. This model will provide a good understanding of the behaviour of Gaia, allowing in the future a better calibration of the attitude.

However, this model is not suited for the simulation purposes of CU2, and specially for the simplified requirements of cycle 3. It is computationally too intensive to be of practical use for GASS simulations and is not implemented in Java.

Therefore, a simpler stochastic model of the Gaia attitude is presented in this section to be used in cycle 3 simulations. This model can evolve in the future and become more sophisticated, including supplementary effects or more refined noise models.

3.2 Stochastic model of the attitude for simulations

In each axis the deviation of the true attitude from the NSL is simulated as a second-order stationary Markov process. Using a constant time step Δt , let x_k be the error in position (angle)

at time $k\Delta t$, v_k the error in angular velocity (rate), and a_k the error in angular acceleration. Then the propagation from t_k to t_{k+1} is accomplished by:

$$a_k = -v_k/\tau_v - x_k/\tau_x^2 + n_k \quad (1)$$

$$v_{k+1} = v_k + a_k\Delta t \quad (2)$$

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + v_k\Delta t \quad (3)$$

where τ_v , τ_x are the time constants for the on-board attitude control in velocity and position. n_k is white gaussian noise with variance $\sigma_n^2 = P_a/\Delta t$, where P_a is the PSD of the acceleration noise from the thrusters (assumed to be constant over the relevant frequency range, i.e. below ~ 1 Hz).

In steady-state, the standard deviations in velocity and position are

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}P_a\tau_v} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_x = \sigma_v\tau_x \quad (5)$$

Moreover, v_k and x_k are uncorrelated, so the Markov chain can be started (for $k = 0$) with¹

$$v_0 \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2), \quad x_0 \sim N(0, \sigma_x^2) \quad (6)$$

and of course $n_0 \sim N(0, \sigma_n^2)$, whereupon (1)–(3) gives successive points in the time series. The properties of the time series (i.e., the total variance and power spectrum well below the Nyquist frequency) are in principle independent of the time step Δt . It should only be chosen small enough that interpolation errors are negligible. Probably $\Delta t = 0.1$ s could be used, or even $\Delta t = 1$ s.

Three independent random processes $x(t)$, $y(t)$, $z(t)$ (in rad) have to be generated in parallel,

¹ $g \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ means the generation of an independent gaussian variate with mean value μ and variance σ^2 .

corresponding to the three axes; then the attitude quaternion is modified according to

$$\mathbf{q}(t) = \mathbf{q}_{\text{NSL}}(t) \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}x(t) \\ \frac{1}{2}y(t) \\ \frac{1}{2}z(t) \\ \sqrt{1 - (\frac{1}{2}x(t))^2 - (\frac{1}{2}y(t))^2 - (\frac{1}{2}z(t))^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

It remains to determine the parameters P_a , τ_v and τ_x that define the power spectrum of the attitude errors. In principle they should be different in the three axes, but we propose using conservative (small) values in all three axes in the cycle 3 simulation, by matching the parameters to reasonable errors in the AL direction (z axis). For instance,

$$P_a = 1.0 \times 10^{-18} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-4} \text{ Hz}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$\tau_v = 50 \text{ s} \quad (9)$$

$$\tau_x = 50 \text{ s} \quad (10)$$

gives $\sigma_v \simeq 1 \text{ mas s}^{-1}$ and $\sigma_x \simeq 50 \text{ mas}$. Figs. 1 and 2 show the result of a simulation using the above parameters and a time step of 1 s.

The power spectral density (PSD) of $x(t)$, in the limit of small Δt , is

$$P_x(f) = \frac{2P_a\tau_x^4}{1 - \left(2 - \left(\frac{\tau_x}{\tau_v}\right)^2\right) (2\pi f\tau_x)^2 + (2\pi f\tau_x)^4} \quad (11)$$

It can be noted that $\tau_x \simeq \tau_v$ gives critical damping of oscillations. The PSD is essentially flat up to the control bandwidth frequency $f_x = (2\pi\tau_x)^{-1}$, after which it decreases as f^{-4} . Figure 3 shows the estimated PSD (amplitude of the discrete Fourier transform, properly scaled) from the simulations, together with the theoretical PSD from (11).

Figure 1: **Left:** simulation of the position (angle) error in x , using parameters in (8) and time step $\Delta t = 1$ s. **Right:** Same as left on a zoomed scale.

Figure 2: **Left:** simulation of the velocity (rate) error in x , using parameters in (8) and time step $\Delta t = 1$ s. **Right:** Same as left on a zoomed scale.

4 Adaptation to GASS simulations

In cycle 3 the ‘attitude with filtered white noise’ described here will be used in the GASS data generator ([YI06]). GASS is designed to simulate large amounts of Gaia telemetry using simplified models of the observations (analytical when possible) for speed.

The details of the attitude simulation are mostly relevant for astrometric purposes, those affecting the AGIS solutions. Some details of the GASS simulation of astrometry are provided below and from them some conclusions for the application of the noisy attitude model described in Section 3 are drawn.

Before discussing the implementation in the simulator, let’s define some terms:

Figure 3: Estimated PSD (red) from the simulation in Figs. 1–2, and the theoretical PSD (blue) from (11). The horizontal axis is frequency in Hz, the vertical is the square-root of the PSD, in $\text{mas Hz}^{-1/2}$.

- The basic reference for the attitude is the Nominal Scanning Law (NSL). We will denote an ideal attitude following exactly the NSL as the **Nominal attitude**.
- The **True attitude** for the satellite will be in practice inaccessible. It will contain noise at all frequencies and have a very complex structure. We will not deal with this one.
- What we will in practice deal with is the **Effective attitude**, the result of filtering the true attitude through the TDI integration time of the observations in the CCDs. A more detailed discussion on this concept can be found in [BB05].

With these definitions in mind the guidelines for the implementation of the “attitude with filtered white noise” in GaiaSimu are given here.

4.1 Astrometry simulation in GASS

Given an object entering the Gaia focal plane, the simulation of AF windows in GASS is composed of several steps:

Detection: selection according to detection criteria and generation of detection information.

Selection of the window type: the type of window to generate is selected depending on the magnitude of the object.

Selection of a PSF/LSF: a PSF/LSF is selected ² depending on the position in the focal plane. The PSF/LSF used are **effective**, as opposed to optical. This means they contain the added effect of several phenomena (TDI unaccuracies, deviations from nominal scan velocity, attitude jitter, etc.) that affect the observation during a CCD crossing, causing a widening (blurring) with respect to the optical PSF/LSF.

Generation of the window: the PSF/LSF is placed on the window taking into account all the relevant effects (geometry, attitude, chromaticity, etc.).

For what concerns the attitude, this process can then be conceptually divided in two parts:

1. The high frequency noise (below the CCD crossing time) is taken into account into the generation of the effective PSF/LSF, amounting to a widening or blurring with respect to the optical ones.
2. The low frequency noise (of the order of the CCD crossing time or above) has to be taken into account in the “placing” of the windows and the PSF/LSF inside the windows.

4.2 Implementation of a noisy attitude

From the discussion in the previous section it is clear that what is needed for the GASS simulations is the “low frequency effects” in the attitude. As mentioned above, this corresponds to timescales of the order of the CCD crossing time or above. This crossing time will vary from bright to faint stars due to the use of the CCD gates, but for cycle 3 we can ignore this distinction and use the full CCD crossing time, which is of the order of 4.4 s.

In short, what we will “see” in the position of the AF windows in Gaia observations will be the result of the true attitude filtered through a “low bandpass filter” of the order of 4.4 s.

Taking this into account the proposal for the implementation in the simulator can be summarised as follows:

- The parameters used for the noise generation are:

$$P_a = 5.0 \times 10^{-20} \text{ rad}^2 \text{ s}^{-4} \text{ Hz}^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$\tau_v = 50 \text{ s} \quad (13)$$

$$\tau_x = 50 \text{ s} \quad (14)$$

²this feature is present in GASS but is not yet used; presently a single PSF/LSF is used for all the focal plane

- The time step for the simulation of the attitude noise will be 1 s. Therefore the noise in each axis – $x(t)$, $y(t)$, $z(t)$ – will be generated as a single Markov chain for the full mission with 1 s steps
- One value in four (one each 4 seconds) will be used to fit splines. These splines will represent the “effective attitude” to be used in the GASS simulations; the value of this “effective attitude” can be obtained at any time by using spline interpolation between the 4-second nodes. Effects of noise with higher frequencies will be assumed to be included in the PSF/LSF.
- For practical reasons a full spline fitting of the noise at the sampling points from mission begin to mission end is not presently feasible. Therefore the spline fitting of the noise will be divided in *Noise Fitting Intervals* (NFI). The NFI length will be defined to optimise the computation time.
- Inside each NFI and a spline fit will be made independently of the adjacent NFIs. Therefore the continuity of the attitude is assured between NFIs, but not of its derivative. However the effect in the derivative is quite small.
- The noise thus interpolated, one value for each quaternion component, will be multiplied by the nominal attitude (nominal quaternion) as described in Equation 7, providing the effective attitude (effective quaternion) to be used by GASS.
- The effects of attitude discontinuities caused by micrometeoroid impacts are not included in this procedure.

4.3 Results

The above described procedure has been implemented in the *Attitude* class of the GaiaSimu library. The results in Table 1 have been obtained for the simulation of a time interval of a few days:

Component	Mean [mas]	Standard deviation [mas]
$x(t)$	0.04	11.61
$y(t)$	0.02	11.71
$z(t)$	0.08	11.67

Table 1: means and standard deviations for the three noise components of the effective attitude (spline interpolation). These values have been obtained by sampling the effective attitude at steps of 1 s over a 300,000 seconds interval

Figure 4 depicts the results for a 80000 s interval and Figures 5 and 6 show a zoom-in for a smaller interval. In Figure 6 the differences between the generated chain (at 1 s steps) and the spline interpolation can be observed.

Figure 4: simulation of the position (angle) error in x ; this plot is similar to the left panel of Figure 1, generated independently by L. Lindegren, but in this case the simulation has been made with 20 times smaller acceleration noise power (P_a) thus having a $\sqrt{20}$ times smaller amplitude.

Figure 5: zoom-in of the previous figure. This plot is similar to the right panel of Figure 1, generated independently by L. Lindgren, but in this case the simulation has been made with 20 times smaller acceleration noise power (P_a) thus having a $\sqrt{20}$ times smaller amplitude.

Figure 6: Fine details of the results of the simulation. **Black dots:** points of the Markov chain at 1 s step. **Red circles:** points of the chain used for the spline fitting (4 s steps). **Line:** result of the spline interpolation (effective attitude).